

Disease reactions 15 and 35 DAI. Faizabad District, U.P., India.

Representative test varieties	Disease-score ^a		Type of reaction ^b	Varieties (no.)
	15 DAI	35 DAI		
Anjani III, Bishunbhog, Damodar, IR20, Randhuri, Zeerabatti	1	1	R	7
Chinidardi, Dehradun (Mota), Dhurigabha, Gallor, Gajraj, Kala Namak	1	3	MR (SB)	11
Katri, Loungchoor, Rambhog, Saraya, Sita, Surajpankhi 374	3	3	MR	10
Chameli	1	5	MS (VSB)	1
Beni, Benideoria, Gaurea, Mutmuri, Pankhali, Shyamzsera	3	5	MS (SB)	24
Adamchini, Amgandh, Badshah Pasand, Bhagalpuri, Ramjas	5	5	MS	29
Agwar, Bilaspur, Delha, Dadhaha, Sonachoor, FRG10	3	7	S (VSB)	6
Ashahniya, Basahwa, Dudaha, Jaisuria, Lalkibhadai, Sumokhan	5	7	S (SB)	13
Bajri, Bakki, Karhan, Kotabasmati, Mirchbooti, Motibadam	7	7	S	13
Champa (C), Kalamdan, Mutra, Sukhwan, Tinpakhiya, Agtahwa (FD)	5	9	HS (VSB)	9
Gheebhat, Kalakand, Karnya, Kashi P.D., Madhukar, Ramkajra	7	9	HS (SB)	11
Anand, Anjana, Bindibali, Bindikali, Gajgaur, TN1	9	9	HS	30

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980). ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible, SB = slow blighting, VSB = very slow blighting.

infection within 15 DAI; others took more time (see table).

The results indicate the limitations of recording observations only at 15 DAI. It is possible to divide reaction groups into normal blighting, slow blighting, and very slow blighting varieties. □

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Insect resistance

Incorporation of brown planthopper (BPH) resistance genes from indica into japonica rice

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None of the 8,200 japonica varieties or lines we screened in 1976-82 were resistant to BPH. Resistance genes can only be found in the tall traditional indica varieties of South Asia. We transferred BPH resistance genes from indica to two japonica lines (80047 and 80079) in 1980. Using those lines as resistance sources, several promising japonica lines resistant to BPH have been developed (see table).

- 864 derived from Yan Keng 2//791943/80047 yields 8 t/ha, 10% more than widely grown Yan Keng 2 and is suitable for single and double cropping in the Chang Jiang River

Yield performance and insect resistance of promising japonica lines. Jiangsu, China, 1987.

Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./ plant)	Grains (no./ panicle)	Sterility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Resistance		
								BPH	BB	BI
864	147	100-105	9	120	8	26.0	8.0	MR	R	R
870064	155	90-95	9	146	14.2	25.3	7.9	R	R	R
850041	150	95-100	8	116	24.0	23.0	7.0	R	R	MR

basin. It is resistant to bacterial blight (BB) and moderately resistant to BPH and blast (BI). Its grain quality is acceptable to consumers.

- 870664 (Yan Keng 2//791943/80047//Non Ken 57/IR26) yields 8 t/ha and is suitable for the Tai-hu Lake basin and the

Chang Jiang River basin. It is resistant to BPH, BI, and BB.

- 850041 derived from 791943/80047 has large panicles, but unsatisfactory lodging resistance. Average yields are 7 t/ha. It is highly resistant to BPH and BB, but susceptible to sheath blight. □

Screening rice seedlings for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

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We screened 26 accessions from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project at the seedling stage for

resistance to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* in the 1987 wet season.

Pregerminated seeds were sown 6 cm apart in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. Six rows of each accession were planted across the width of the seedbox, for 3 plants/hill, 5 hills/row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and one row of resistant check Ptb 33 were sown at random in each seedbox.